

Dipole Moments of some Naphthalene Derivatives. A Study of the Conformational Preferences of Substituent Groups

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The electric dipole moments of more than fifty naphthalene derivatives have been determined. Steric, polar and field effects existing in disubstituted naphthalenes are studied by comparing the observed dipole moments with those calculated by vector addition of group moments. The conformational preferences of the substituent groups in a number of disubstituted naphthalenes are discussed. The methoxy group prefers an *s-cis* orientation to the *ortho*-position of higher π -electron density whereas the acetyl group prefers the *s-trans* orientation between the carbonyl group and the *ortho*-position of higher electron density. This is a consequences of the 1-2 bond of naphthalene being more double-bond-like than the 2-3 bond.

The early work to measure and interpret the dipole moments of naphthalene derivatives was mainly aimed at making a comparison of the moments of isometric monosubstituted naphthalenes, and making a comparison of these moments with those of the corresponding monosubstituted benzenes¹. Later work was mostly concerned with study of the conformations of some mono- and disubstituted naphthalenes with the aid of dipole moments and molar Kerr constants^{2,3}. The zero or near-zero moments observed for 1,5- and 2,6-dimethyl⁴, 1,5- and 2,6-dichloro⁵ and 1,5-dinitro⁶ naphthalenes indicate the naphthalene molecule to be planar and symmetrical. However, disubstituted compounds with identical substituents at 1- and 4-positions do possess a definite moment, e.g. 1,4-dichloro⁵ (0.50 D), 1,4-dibromo⁷ (0.41 D) and 1,4-dinitro⁶ (1.42 D). The distinction establishes the existence of induced moment of the substituent in the unsubstituted ring and evokes interest for an examination of the dipole moments of more naphthalene derivatives.

The paucity of dipole moment data on di- and polysubstituted naphthalenes and the indication, by Nuclear Overhauser Effect (NOE) difference spectroscopy, of the preferential orientation of COCH₃

and OCH₃ groups attached to the naphthalene system^{8,9} prompted the present work.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data are given in Table 1. The computed data for monosubstituted naphthalenes with axial group moments are given in Table 2. While computing the dipole moment of a monosubstituted naphthalene, the molecule was regarded as a substituted benzene to which a polarisable system is attached. This polarisable system consists of 4 C-H and its polarisability (α) was taken as two-thirds of that of benzene⁵. The permanent dipole moment μ of the substituent induces moments μ_x and μ_y respectively, parallel and perpendicular in direction to that of μ where

$$\mu_x = \frac{\epsilon + 2}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha\mu(3\cos^2\theta - 1)}{\epsilon r^3}$$

$$\mu_y = \frac{\epsilon + 2}{3} \cdot \frac{\alpha\mu(3\sin\theta \cos\theta)}{\epsilon r^3}$$

where r is distance between the polarisable centre and the point of action of the principal moment,

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TABLE 1-POLARISATION DATA

Nahthalene	α	$-\beta$	γ	∞P_2 ml	R_D ml	μ^w D
2-Br	1.75	0.444	0.267	114.0	54.4	1.72 ^a
1-NO ₂	9.83	0.340	0.394	362.4	51.4	3.93 ^b
2-NO ₂	11.71	0.369	0.386	426.0	52.5	4.31 ^c
1-NH ₂	2.06	0.271	0.466	93.5	49.6	1.48 ^d
2-NH ₂	2.62	0.237	0.473	110.2	51.2	1.71 ^e
2-N(CH ₃) ₂	2.63	0.198	0.403	133.9	60.9	1.90
1-OCH ₃	1.33	0.244	0.300	82.7	51.1	1.25 ^f
2-OCH ₃	1.21	0.246	0.317	79.0	51.5	1.17 ^g
1-SCH ₃	1.35	0.282	0.415	89.5	58.1	1.25 ^h
2-SCH ₃	1.42	0.255	0.467	93.3	61.3	1.26
1-COCH ₃	5.52	0.272	0.332	222.8	54.5	2.89
2-COCH ₃	6.22	0.253	0.335	246.7	55.3	3.08
1-OPh	0.946	0.293	0.364	95.7	68.6	1.16
2-OPh	1.13	0.276	0.345	100.0	70.8	1.21
2-SPh	1.48	0.305	0.479	125.8	80.5	1.50
1-SO ₂ Ph	10.33	0.409	0.315	585.5	74.3	5.04
2-SO ₂ Ph	10.81	0.390	0.399	617.2	80.2	5.17
1-SO ₂ CH ₃	11.91	0.377	0.318	514.3	59.2	4.75
2-SO ₂ CH ₃	12.27	0.380	0.313	528.0	58.8	4.83
1-NO ₂ -2-CH ₃	7.17	0.301	0.325	301.2	56.9	3.49
1-NO ₂ -2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	7.24	0.309	0.293	327.4	60.9	3.64
1-NO ₂ -2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	7.25	0.293	0.320	326.9	61.2	3.64
4-NO ₂ -1-NH ₂	22.45	0.412	—	844.7	63.8*	6.23
4-NO ₂ -1-NH ₂ *	31.63	0.258	0.863	1028.5	63.8	6.92 ⁱ
6-NO ₂ -2-NH ₂	23.43	0.257	—	888.8	66.5*	6.39 ^j
8-NO ₂ -2-NH ₂	12.28	0.410	0.588	481.0	61.0	4.57 ^k
2-CH ₃ -4-NO ₂ -1-NH ₂	19.83	0.392	—	855.3	66.4*	6.26
2-CH ₃ -4-NO ₂ -1-NH ₂ *	28.38	0.215	0.762	998.0	66.4	6.81
4-NO ₂ -1-N(CH ₃) ₂	14.99	0.351	0.605	66.8	75.7	5.42
4-SO ₂ CH ₃ -1-NH ₂	18.36	0.440	—	766.1	59.6*	5.93
4-SO ₂ CH ₃ -1-NH ₂ *	24.00	0.257	0.578	869.9	59.6	6.35
1-OCH ₃ -2-NO ₂	10.01	0.367	0.353	434.0	60.3	4.31 ^l
1-OCH ₃ -3-NO ₂	7.84	0.376	0.315	349.8	58.3	3.81
1-OCH ₃ -4-NO ₂	12.54	0.374	0.435	531.2	63.1	4.82 ^m
1-OCH ₃ -5-NO ₂	12.09	0.374	0.435	509.6	55.0	4.75
1-OCH ₃ -6-NO ₂	16.24	0.452	0.344	667.9	54.4	5.52
2-OCH ₃ -1-NO ₂	11.20	0.493	0.390	479.2	60.9	4.56 ⁿ
2-OCH ₃ -3-NO ₂	11.46	0.374	0.381	489.3	61.5	4.61
2-OCH ₃ -4-NO ₂	11.25	0.383	0.407	479.4	55.4	4.59
2-OCH ₃ -5-NO ₂	12.54	0.419	0.303	530.5	63.2	4.82
2-OCH ₃ -6-NO ₂	13.64	0.389	0.458	571.8	62.8	5.03
2-OCH ₃ -8-NO ₂	5.65	0.385	0.445	266.6	64.6	3.17
1-NO ₂ -2-SCH ₃	10.16	0.346	0.431	461.1	61.2	4.46
		0.353	0.581			

1-NO ₂ -4-SCH ₃	8 90	0 397	0 480	419 1	68 5	4 18
2,6-(OCH ₃) ₂	1 23	0 267	0 335	93 1	60 7	1 27
2-OCH ₃ -6-Br	2 72	0 482	0 305	169 6	60 2	2 33
1-OCH ₃ -2-COCH ₃	5 16	0 280	0 301	247 9	62 5	3 04 ^P
1-OCH ₃ -4-COCH ₃	4 40	0 296	0 369	388 9	64 2	4 02 ^P
2-OCH ₃ -1-COCH ₃	7 50	0 308	0 326	334 2	60 8	3 69
2-OCH ₃ -6-COCH ₃	6 66	0 303	0 295	304 5	61 4	3 48
2-COCH ₃ -6-Cl	3 15	0 349	0 337	171 3	61 2	2 12
2-COCH ₃ -6-Br	2 72	0 492	0 340	151 0	64 3	2 08
2-COCH ₃ -6-SCH ₃	5 22	0 324	0 515	247 6	73 7	2 94
<i>Benzene derivative</i>						
2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ SCH ₃	15 18	0 401	0 365	526 0	48 9	4 87
4-NO ₂ -2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₂ NH ₂	27 01	0 399	—	890 6	52 3 [*]	6 43
4-NO ₂ -2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₂ NI ₂ [*]	34 34	0 183	0 638	966 9	52 3	6 74

^PLit. values²² in Debye units : ^a1.70, 1.73; ^b3.91, 3.98, ^c4.39, 4.40; ^d1.45, 1.50; ^e1.76, ^f1.26, 1.22, ^g1.11; ^h1.27; ⁱ6.43; ^j7.15; ^k4.50; ^l5.04; ^m5.19; ⁿ4.66; ^p3.35; ^q4.02. In dioxane.

θ the angle between the direction of r and μ and ϵ the dielectric constant of the medium. The induced moments μ_x and μ_y are taken to act at the mass centre of the unsubstituted ring. The value of α is taken as $0.667 \times 12.5 \times 10^{-24}$ (2/3 of the benzene value) and the value of ϵ as 2.27, same as that of benzene. The values of θ , μ and r depend upon the nature and position of the substituent. A critical account of this method is given by Smith¹⁰ and Smyth¹¹.

TABLE 2—MONOSUBSTITUTED NAPHTHALENES HAVING AXIAL GROUP-MOMENTS*

Substituent	r Å	θ deg	μ_{calc} D	μ_{obs} D
1-F	3 71	54 7	1 45	1 43
2-F	5 00	17 8	1 53	1 50
1-Cl	3 82	52 5	1 60	1 60
2-Cl	5 18	17 0	1 67	1 74
1-Br	3 83	52 2	1 58	1 58
2-Br	5 19	16 9	1 65	1 72
1-I	3 90	51 0	1 39	1 44
2-I	5 30	16 7	1 45	1 57
1-NO ₂	4 16	46 7	4 09	3 93
2-NO ₂	5 68	15 5	4 15	4 31

*Values for 2-bromo-, 1-nitro- and 2-nitronaphthalenes are from the present work. Other values are from literature²².

For the calculations made, the following bond distances (in Å) were assumed : C-C 1.40, C-N 1.45, C-O 1.36, C-S 1.75, C-F 1.50, C-Cl 1.77, C-Br 1.89 and C-I 2.10. In the case of methyl and halogeno substituents, the principal dipole was considered to be located at the mid-point of the line joining the ring carbon with the substituent. For methoxy, acetyl, nitro and methylthio groups, the principal moment was taken to reside on oxygen, carbonyl carbon, nitrogen and sulphur respectively. The values of the principal moments (in Debye units) used for the calculation were those of the corresponding benzene derivatives¹² : PhF 1.43, PhCl 1.57, PhBr 1.55, PhI 1.36, PhNO₂ 3.95, PhCOCH₃ 2.90, PhOCH₃ 1.25, PhSCH₃ 1.31. The dipole inclinations of the groups OCH₃ and SCH₃ were taken as 75° and 102° respectively¹², and that of COCH₃ as 125°¹⁶.

A comparison of the calculated and experimental values (Table 2) shows that the agreement between them is good or excellent except for 2-Cl-, 2-Br-, 2-I- and nitronaphthalenes. The observation in respect of 2-Cl, 2-Br and 2-I compounds is significant as well as interesting and it will be discussed later in the context of 6-Cl- and 6-Br-2-acetyl naphthalenes. In the case of the nitro compounds, while the conjugation of the 1-NO₂ group may be expected

to be diminished due to *peri*-methine hindrance¹³ leading to a smaller moment, the 2-nitro group can cause a higher moment by virtue of the longer conjugated system that is possible when the 2-NO₂ group interacts with the naphthyl group.

Table 3 presents the data of some monosubstituted naphthalenes for which the group moments are nonaxial. The observed dipole moment of 1-methoxynaphthalene agrees with the value calculated for a conformation which is not probable. Models reveal considerable hindrance to the *cis* arrangement of *peri*-hydrogen and the methoxymethyl. The other but the more probable conformation leads to a high value. It was estimated² that in the *cis* arrangement the van der Waals zones of *O*-methyl and C₈-H interpenetrate by ~1.1 Å while in the *trans* arrangement this overlap is only 0.1 Å. On the basis of Kerr constant measurements a nonplanar model was suggested² with an interplanar angle of 19°.

TABLE 3—MONOSUBSTITUTED NAPHTHALENE HAVING NONAXIAL GROUP-MOMENTS

Compd no	<i>r</i> Å	θ (deg)	μ_{calc} / μ_{obs} D
1	4.10	302.7	1.25 (1.25)
2	4.10	152.7	1.39 (1.25)
3	5.59	270.7	1.21 (1.17)
4	5.59	120.7	1.24
5	4.18	351.5	3.30 (2.89)
6	4.18	101.5	2.67 (2.89)
7	5.71	320.5	2.97 (3.08)
8	5.71	70.5	2.85 (3.08)
9	4.37	329.1	1.41 (1.25)
10	4.37	124.1	1.31 (1.25)
11	5.97	297.2	1.30 (1.26)
12	5.97	93.2	1.28 (1.26)

For the 2-methoxynaphthalene a slight preference

of conformation **3** is indicated, though the calculated moments for **3** and **4** do not differ much. This preference is a consequence of the 1-2 bond of naphthalene having more double bond character than the 2-3 bond¹⁴. In conformation **3** the methoxy group is *s-cis* to the double bond and from electronic considerations it should be more stable than **4** in which the lone-pair electrons of oxygen are *cis* to the double bond. NOE difference spectroscopy also shows such a conformational preference^{8,9}.

The observed dipole moment of 1-acetylnaphthalene does not correspond to the value calculated for either of the conformation **5** and **6**. This is to be expected because there will be considerable nonbonded interaction of the carbonyl oxygen or the methyl with the *peri*-hydrogen. A nonplanar variation of **6** was suggested², the interplanar angle being about 30.5°. Though free rotation of the acetyl group of 2-acetylnaphthalene is possible, the values given in Table 3 indicate that **7** is the preferred conformation. NOE difference spectroscopy also points to this preference¹⁵.

In the case of 1-naphthyl methyl sulphide, the *trans* arrangement of *S*-Me and *peri*-hydrogen is preferred. This is in agreement with expectation. For the 2-isomer the value calculated for **11** or **12** is in agreement with the observed value. As stated for its oxygen analogue, **11** is, however, the preferred conformation.

The steric and polar effects in many disubstituted and a few trisubstituted naphthalene derivatives have also been studied by comparing the observed dipole moments with those calculated by the vector addition of group moments. The moment of the appropriate monosubstituted naphthalene derivative was taken as the individual group moment.

The methyl substituent at 2-position suppresses the conjugation of the nitro group with the ring system in 1-nitro-2-methylnaphthalene (μ_{calc} 3.75, μ_{obs} 3.49 D). Steric inhibition of resonance also exists in 2,3-dimethyl-1-nitronaphthalene (μ_{calc} 4.00, μ_{obs} 3.64 D) and 2,6-dimethyl-1-nitronaphthalene (μ_{calc} 3.93, μ_{obs} 3.64 D). The former compound

was examined to see if the vicinal methyl group exerts any buttressing effect, enhancing the conjugation of the nitro group.

The 1,4-conjugation of NH_2 and SO_2CH_3 groups is weak in the naphthalene system compared with the benzene system. The dipole moment of methyl 4-aminophenyl sulphone¹⁷ is 6.09 D as against the calculated value of 5.58 D taking the dipole inclination of NH_2 group¹² as 48° and that of SO_2CH_3 group as 138° (calculated from the dipole moments of methyl *m*-chlorophenyl sulphone¹⁸ 4.33 D, methyl phenyl sulphone¹⁸ 4.66 D and chlorobenzene 1.57 D); the interaction moment is thus 0.51 D. The dipole moment of methyl 1-amino-4-naphthyl sulphone is 5.93 D, whereas the calculated value is 5.63 D. The interaction moment, 0.30 D, is thus lower than that of the benzene analogue.

The conjugation in heteronuclear nitroamines was studied by measuring the dipole moments of 6-nitro- and 8-nitro-2-naphthylamines. Both the compounds are associated with large interaction moments : 0.79 D for the 6-nitro compound (μ_{obs} 6.39 D, μ_{calc} 5.60 D) and 0.84 D for the 8-nitro isomer (μ_{obs} 4.57 D, μ_{calc} 3.73 D). These values suggest a significant contribution from structures 13 and 14 to their molecules.

A major objective of this investigation was to determine and analyse the dipole moments of all the isomeric methoxynitronaphthalenes. In spite of the efforts made to prepare all the fourteen possible isomers, only eleven could be prepared in amounts sufficient for measurements. The moments expected for several conformations and for free rotation of groups were calculated.

In 1-methoxy-2-nitronaphthalene, free rotation of the groups is improbable. The apparent agreement of the free rotation value (4.33 D) with the observed value (4.31 D) is fortuitous. The nearness of the value 4.17 D, calculated for a conformation with orthogonal methoxyl, to the observed value may be considered satisfactory considering the fact that the mutual induction of substituents was not taken into account in the calculation. In the other 1-methoxynitronaphthalenes, the observed values can be best explained by assuming a preferred orientation of OCH_3 *trans* to the *peri*-hydrogen. This should also be the natural preference¹³. The observed dipole moment (4.82 D) of 1-methoxy-4-nitronaphthalene is significantly higher than the moment (4.43 D) calculated for any of its conformers. This is due to a mesomeric component in it.

In the case of 2-methoxynitronaphthalenes, there can be free rotation of groups except for 1-nitro and 3-nitro isomers but the dipole moments calculated for such free rotation do not agree well with the observed values. For the 6-nitro compound, the calculated dipole moment for free rotation of groups or any possible conformation is 4.75 D whereas the observed moment is 5.03 D. The slightly higher observed value is due to the conjugation of CH_3O and NO_2 groups, which is obviously weak. For the other isomers, the observed dipole moment is nearer to the one calculated for the conformation (15) in which the methoxy group is oriented towards the 1-2 bond which has a higher double bond

	4-NO ₂	5-NO ₂	8-NO ₂
μ_{obs}	4.59	4.82	3.17 D
μ_{calc}	5.07	5.07	2.82 D

	4-NO ₂	5-NO ₂	8-NO ₂
μ_{calc}	3.21	3.21	4.83 D

character than the 2-3 bond as stated earlier.

Such orientation of the methoxy group keeps the nonbonded electrons of oxygen away from the π -electrons of the adjacent double bond. This is also the conformational preference of OCH₃ in 2-methoxynaphthalene.

The observed dipole moment (1.27 D) of 2,6-dimethoxynaphthalene is considerably lower than the calculated value (1.60 D) for free rotation of groups indicating preferential orientation of the methoxy groups towards the adjacent double bonds (17).

The dipole moments of 2-acetyl-6-chloro- and 2-acetyl-6-bromonaphthalenes offer an interesting study. The former has a moment of 2.12 D and the latter 2.08 D. The moments calculated for free rotation are 2.53 and 2.58 D, respectively. Thus the observed values are unexpectedly lower. Here the preferred orientation of the acetyl group should have no effect unless the halogen also takes a preferred orientation. One might not normally think of such a preferred orientation for the halogen

X = Cl or Br

but the halogen might be inclined away from the double bond (18) due to the repulsion between the lone-pair electrons of the halogen and the adjacent π -electrons. Even a small angle of deflection can explain the observed phenomenon. The calculated dipole moments of 2-chloro-, 2-bromo- and 2-iodonaphthalenes being lower than the observed dipole moments (Table 2) are also explicable on the basis of such a disposition of the halogen substituents in respect of the double bond. The X-ray crystallographic data of 2,3,4,5,6-pentachlorocyclohexene¹⁹ (19) provides evidence for a halogen substituent deflecting away from the double bond. The angle *ba* is 113°.

The view that the chloro and bromo substituents of 18 are deflected away from the double bond gets strengthened by the fact that the difference between the observed and calculated moments for the chloro compound is 0.41 D while the same for the bromo compound is 0.50 D. The higher difference for the bromo compound becomes explicable on the ground that the larger Br is repelled by the π -electrons to a greater extent than the smaller Cl.

Experimental

The dielectric constant, density and refractive index of solutions were measured at 30° with the apparatus described earlier²⁰. Definitions of symbols used and the method of calculating the dipole moment were the same as reported earlier²⁰. The solvent used was benzene unless stated it to be dioxane. The dielectric constant, density and refractive index were determined on three to five solutions of graded concentrations, so choosing them that the most concentrated solution had a dielectric constant not more than about 0.4 units greater than that of the solvent

used. The dielectric constant, specific volume and refractive index of benzene were taken as 2.2628, 1.1516 and 1.4949 respectively, and those of dioxane as 2.2015, 0.97818 and 1.41805 respectively.

The compounds were prepared as described in the literature and purified rigorously. The solvents, benzene and dioxane, were also well purified.

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